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SCENOGRAPHIC TRADITIONS IN KARAKALPAK OPERA AND BALLET: STAGE SOLUTIONS IN THE BALLET

“NAZLIMKHAN SULUV”

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Abstract. This article provides a scientific analysis of the main characteristics of scenographic traditions developed in Karakalpak opera and ballet and offers a commentary on the stage solutions of the ballet “*Nazlimkhan Suluv*” using a comparative approach grounded in scenography theories. The study’s relevance lies in the need to identify principles for creating artistic space in national ballet and to explore a model of national scenography integrated with contemporary theater technologies.

Keywords: opera, ballet, decoration, sketch, creativity, theater, development, dramaturgy, artist-director.

In our country, the attention that the head of state currently devotes to the field of culture and art—aimed at further developing opera and ballet, widely promoting national opera and ballet, and strengthening its position and status in the world of art—is assessed as greater and more substantial than ever before. In this context, the very adoption of Decree No. PQ-64 on December 27, 2021, by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, titled “*On Measures to Further Develop Opera and Ballet Art*”, is regarded as a significant step with a major impact on the development of the field. [1;65]

In accordance with Decree No. PF-6000 dated May 26, 2020, by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, “*On Measures to Further Enhance the Role and Influence of Culture and Art in Society*”, the priority directions for the development of opera and ballet in the country were defined. Accordingly, issues such as enhancing the prestige of opera and ballet in the process of building a New Uzbekistan and promoting national opera and ballet art on the international stage were advanced. [2;14]

Based on these documents, the following tasks were identified as priority directions:

- Enhancing the prestige of opera and ballet and promoting the national heritage on an international level;
- Bringing national and classical works to a wider audience, particularly expanding cultural recreation opportunities in remote regions;
- Developing national opera and ballet schools, supporting the master–apprentice traditions, and preserving artistic masterpieces;

- Strengthening the system of personnel training, reinforcing cooperation between theaters and educational institutions, and improving the material and technical base;
- Supporting representatives of the arts and promoting the legacy of prominent creators.

These measures ensure the contemporary development of opera and ballet in Uzbekistan and contribute to elevating the creative processes to a qualitatively new level.

As a practical result of these efforts, the premiere of the ballet “*Nazlimkhan Suluv*” by Q. Zaretdinov—an artist who has served both the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Karakalpakstan—was held at the Berdakh Karakalpak State Academic Musical Theater. The libretto was authored by Z. Nurimbetov, People’s Artist of Karakalpakstan and Honored Artist of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The stage decorations were created by Barlyqbay Aytmuratov, People’s Artist of Karakalpakstan, Berdakh Prize laureate, and theater designer, together with the theater’s chief designer Zauqi Soipov. The costumes, designed by artist Bakhtiyar Serekeev, complemented the overall artistic integrity of the performance.

In particular, the stage decorations and scenographic solutions of the ballet artistically interpret the key values of our national heritage, incorporating images from the Mizdaqkhan complex—a symbol of our centuries-old history—harmonized with the performers’ mastery. This, as outlined in the aforementioned decrees, serves as a practical embodiment of the objectives to promote national opera and ballet art internationally, preserve masterpieces, and revive them in a contemporary interpretation. The artistic interpretation of motifs from the Mizdaqkhan complex on stage, and the expression of national values through modern scenography, constitute the central artistic and aesthetic core of the ballet. “*Nazlimkhan Suluv*”, our invaluable heritage and unparalleled jewel represented in the Mizdaqkhan complex, was performed with exceptional skill and artistry.

The events of the ballet are based on a beautiful legend preserved among the people about the Nazlimkhan Suluv mausoleum. According to the tale, one of the local rulers intended to marry off his daughter and set an extraordinary condition to find a worthy suitor: whoever could construct an architectural masterpiece that would astonish the world would win her hand. A young man in love with the princess built a palace underground, leaving its dome above the ground. However, the ruler demanded that he prove his love by throwing himself from the unfinished dome. The young man accepted this condition and sacrificed his life, a dramatic act that is artistically expressed in this ballet.

Practical Application of Pictorial Scenography Tools in the Ballet “*Nazlimkhan Suluv*”

In decorating opera and ballet performances, pictorial (painting-based) scenery is often widely used. Primarily, the artist works on a flat surface to draw various visual scenes, which can be landscapes or interiors. The artist may attempt to

construct them in three dimensions. There may also be conventional decorative motifs that create a visual background for the movement of the performance. Ultimately, the artist is capable of actively expressing the idea of the performance on the backdrop, curtain, or special surface using the language of painting or graphics, creating a comprehensive visual metaphor. Scenic decoration opens up countless possibilities for stage solutions for the artist. It is particularly common in opera and ballet performances, though it can also be effectively used in dramatic scenes. [3;36]

The distinctive methods of shaping the stage space through artistic and pictorial means were also vividly demonstrated on the stage of the ballet “*Nazlimkhan Suluv*.” In this performance, pictorial decoration was used as the primary means of expression, since ballet art typically does not require narrative scenery. The stage space, treated as a conventional environment, allows the dance characters to develop freely.

The artists—Barlyqbay Aytmuratov, the theater’s chief designer Zauqi Soipov, and costume designer Bakhtiyar Serekeev—visually expressed the idea of the performance by decorating the stage with pictorial panels. This method, particularly when applied to the backdrop, curtain surfaces, or special panels, allowed the mood of the music and the characters of the ballet to be conveyed to the audience in a powerful visual manner.

While pictorial decoration suits the ballet stage, it is also very convenient under conditions of limited material resources. In the ballet “*Nazlimkhan Suluv*”, it was precisely through such pictorial scenography that a contemporary aesthetic image was created, vividly expressing our national heritage on stage and drawing the audience’s attention to the musical and visual plotlines of the ballet. Thus, in “*Nazlimkhan Suluv*”, pictorial decoration served not only as stage ornamentation but also as the primary artistic tool expressing the idea of the performance, aligning with the state policy and priority objectives aimed at developing opera and ballet art. The state documents adopted within the framework of “*Measures to Develop Opera and Ballet Art in Uzbekistan*” define tasks such as promoting our national art on the international stage, preserving masterpieces, and reviving them in a contemporary interpretation. The ballet “*Nazlimkhan Suluv*” serves as a practical embodiment of this policy, effectively utilizing pictorial scenography to artistically express the stage space.

The pictorial decoration created by the performance’s artists served not only as stage ornamentation but also as the primary artistic tool conveying the idea of the ballet to the audience. The motifs of the Mizdaqkhan complex and the aesthetic interpretation of national values on stage shaped the distinctive image of the ballet, reflecting our national heritage through the lens of contemporary art.

At the same time, the ballet “*Nazlimkhan Suluv*” demonstrated the artistic and aesthetic significance of pictorial scenography on the ballet stage and confirmed its alignment with the state policy aimed at developing opera and ballet art. This

contributes to the recognition and wide promotion of our national art on the international stage.

The current state of a theater with centuries of history is the result of spiritual labor imbued with dedication, skill, and devotion. The theater embarks on its new season with ambitious creative plans, new stage works, and a loyal audience.

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